

QUIZ**LAST NAME: KUSEMERERWA****FIRST NAME: DONNA****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 5****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice 2016 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What is the importance of the story board to the doctoral student?**
 - To provide a visual overview for planning and tracking project implementation.¹**
 - To provide a visual map that their supervisor can use to understand the project
 - To provide a pictorial summary of the completed project.
 - To provide a visual tool for analyzing qualitative aspects of the project.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 22

2. **Which of the following is not a set of primary data sources?**
- Manuscripts, interviews, observations.
 - Manuscripts, observations, demographic and health surveys.
 - Manuscripts, author's own pre-print article, demographic and health surveys.²**
 - Manuscripts, demographic and health surveys, interviews.
3. **Select an incorrect statement on credibility in qualitative research.**
- The longer the involvement of a researcher with study participants the greater the credibility of the study.
 - Credibility is a measure of trust derived primarily from the author's transparency about bias.³**
 - Peer review of participant feedback may contribute to greater accuracy in presenting their thoughts, words and actions.
 - The presentation of negative findings is one way to increase the credibility of a study.

² Turabian 2013, 24.

³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 77.

4. **Which of the following is generally considered acceptable in academic writing?**

- Material from Wikipedia.
- Contractions.
- Uncited works from other authors with similar ideas.
- Personal examples.**⁴

5. **Choose one correct statement about plagiarism.**

- Plagiarism occurs when an author fails to give due credit to their source of information.**⁵
- Common knowledge if not correctly cited constitutes plagiarism.
- Plagiarism cannot result in the revocation of a degree.
- Students need not be concerned about plagiarism for coursework and assignments.

6. **According to the Turabian author-date citation style:**

- A critical source identifier is the publisher.
- The name of the second author in a reference list is given as last name, first name.
- Multiple works by the same author are distinguished by a letter of the alphabet.**⁶
- All initials of authors with the same name are included in the parenthetical citation.

⁴ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 12.

⁵ Turabian, 50.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 133.

7. **The following are the uses of footnotes at the bottom of the table in the WHO style:**

- Indicate the source of a table reproduced from elsewhere.⁷**
- Explain missing entries
- Provide the statistical formula used for the results in the table.
- Elaborate column headings

8. **Which of the following statements would not be considered discriminatory based on the WHO style?**

- Miss Kamala Harris is likely to do a better job in ensuring COVID-19 prevention guidelines are followed than her predecessor.
- According to WHO, a nurse in a rural health center is supposed to have her mask on every time she comes in contact with a patient.
- About 50% of COVID-19 super spreaders are female.⁸**
- Jacinta Ardern has been successful in in dealing with the COVID-19 pandemic in New Zealand despite being a young mother.

9. **Purposeful sampling is used in qualitative research because:**

- It limits study participants to those known by the researcher.
- It allows the results to be generalized to other settings.
- It allows the study to be tailored to the time and money available to the researcher.
- It allows the researcher to target only study participants who can contribute insights to the research questions.⁹**

⁷ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 33.

⁸ *Ibid.*, 54.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 69.

10. Abbreviations:

- Are the same across all disciplines.
- Maybe formed by dropping any of the letters in a word.
- Include initialisms such as UNICEF.**¹⁰
- Include acronyms such as Prof.

¹⁰ Turabian, 196.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.